

Finite and Infinite Geometric Series with Binomial Coefficients

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Abstract: This paper presents a method to compute the finite and infinite geometric series with binomial coefficients. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real-world problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-12], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [11-20] was developed with a new approach of binomial coefficient [19-28].

2. Geometric Series with Binomial Coefficients

A geometric series with binomial coefficients [25-34] is computed by multiple summations of a geometric series [35-42]. The binomial coefficient V_n^r is defined as a coefficient of x^k in the geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i$.

$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ is the geometric series with binomial coefficient V_n^r , whose expansion is given below:

$$V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!},$$

where r is a positive integer and n is a non-negative integer.

Note that $V_n^0 = V_0^0 = 0! = 1$ and $V_0^r = \frac{(0+1)(0+2)(0+3)\cdots(0+r)}{r!} = \frac{r!}{r!} = 1$.

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} V_i^r x^i$ is an infinite geometric series with binomial coefficients.

If $0 < x < 1$, then $\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x^i = \frac{1}{1-x}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} V_i^r x^i = \frac{1}{(1-x)^{r+1}}$.

If $0 < x < 1$, then $\sum_{i=k}^{\infty} x^i = \frac{x^k}{1-x}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=k}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} V_i^r x^i = \frac{x^k}{(1-x)^{r+1}}$.

$$\text{If } 0 < x < 1, \text{ then } \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} ax^i = \frac{a}{1-x} \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r ax^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} V_i^r ax^i = \frac{a}{(1-x)^{r+1}}.$$

$$\text{If } 0 < x < 1, \text{ then } \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} ax^i = \frac{ax^k}{1-x} \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=k}^n V_i^r ax^i = \sum_{i=k}^{\infty} V_i^r ax^i = \frac{ax^k}{(1-x)^{r+1}}.$$

Note that $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ OR $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r ax^i$ is a finite geometric series with binomial coefficients.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the finite and infinite geometric series with binomial coefficients have been discussed and this information can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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